

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Proton SEE Testing of Candidate COTS Electronic Components for a Space Radiation Monitor</i>
Project TA identifier	TA11-366
General application	Space
Type of test	SEE
Group leader, Institute	<i>Melahat Bilge Demirköz, IVMER (The Research and Application Center for Space and Accelerator Technologies)</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Mehlika Zeynep Arslan, Uğur Kılıç, Hazal Düyen, Samet Amanvermez</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>(May 15th - 16th) June 3rd 2025</i>
Facility	UMCG-PARTEC
Amount of access granted	8h

Objectives of the experiments

YRM (Home Grown Radiation Monitor) is being developed for operation on satellites and is designed to measure proton flux between 2 and 200 MeV in 8 bins of kinetic energy and trapped electron flux in Low Earth Orbit for 5 years, with a possible upgrade later for deployment on Geosynchronous Orbit. Development models, called SB.0, consisting of 2 energy bins for protons have flown on sounding rockets [1] and the next version, SB.1 with 4 energy bins for protons, completed its environmental tests and is flight ready. Commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) electronic components are planned to be used in YRM to reduce cost. Therefore, Single Event Effects (SEE) testing and analysis of the critical candidate electronic components is necessary to reduce the operational risk, data loss and loss of communication.

12 of the COTS electronics include two power managers whose product codes are TPS2420RSAT and MAX891LEUA+T respectively, three interface transceivers with product codes PCA82C250T/YM,115, MAX3485AEASA+ and PCA82C250T/YM,115 one interface receiver with product code AM26LS32AIDG4, an interface driver with product code AM26LS31AIDG4, a flash memory with product code MX30LF2G28AD-TI, a sensor with product code LMT01DQXR, a programmable timer with product code SE555DR, an ADC with product code ADC128S102CIMT, a DAC with product code MAX5253BEAP+, alongside with generic transistors and resistors. The components with the specific product codes MAX3485AEASA+ (interface transceivers) and SE555DR (programmable timer) had not been investigated priorly for their readiness to perform in harsh radiation environments.

To predict the SEU rates of candidate components in space and to fit the data into the Weibull function of four variables which describes the dependence of cross section with proton energy, testing of the

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component's SEU cross section with respect to proton energy from threshold energy to saturation energy range at 60-100-150-200 MeV was proposed. A test card containing 12 of the COTS candidate electronic components have been designed. The testing of candidate components with 15 and 30 MeV protons had already been performed at METU-DBL[2]. RADNEXT has granted 8 hours of beamtime at Universite Catholique de Louvain Cyclotron Resource Centre-Light Ion Facility (UCLouvain CRC-LIF) where testing of the 11 of the 12 components has been performed with 60 MeV protons. To continue the scan of the complete proton energy range (20-200 MeV) as is recommended by ESCC, further testing with higher energy protons was need. Therefore, another proposal was made during RADNEXT's 11th call and a beamtime of 8 hours at the PARTEC Proton Irradiation facility has been kindly granted by RADNEXT. As part of Radnext TA-11, the components were tested with protons of kinetic energies 150 MeV and 190 MeV at UMCG-PARTEC. The results have been analyzed and been compared to the tests done with 30, 15 and 60 MeV protons.

Experiment test report

Candidate COTS Devices

List of the candidate COTS devices that were tested and information about them are given below

Device Reference	Device Function	Technology Processes
(1) TPS2420RSAT	Power manager	BiCMOS Texas Instruments "lbc7" process Feature size: 350nm
(2) MAX891LEUA+T	Power manager	CMOS
(4) MAX3485AEASA+	Interface transceiver	Feature size: 800nm
(5),(6)AM26LS31AIDG4/AM26LS32AIDG4	Interface driver/ receiver	Texas Instruments "ji" process
(7) MX30LF2G28AD-TI	Flash memory	Macronix "an" process
(8)LMT01DQXR	Temperature sensor	CMOS
(9)SE555DR	Programmable timer	BJT
(10)ADC128S102CIMT	Analog-to-Digital Converter	Texas Instruments "cmls7" process
(11)MAX5253BEAP+	Digital-to-Analog Converter	CMOS
(12)BC857BS,115	Transistor	BJT

Test Setup and Conditions

The SEE test setup consists of a "Control Card" and a "Test Card". The control card communicates with the test card through UART and SPI interfaces. Using a multiplexer and switching relays, one of 15 addresses which correspond to device under test (DUT) on the test card can be chosen. The control card is built around a PIC microprocessor, DSPIC33CK64MP508, which has 69 I/O pins and CANBUS interfaces as well as 64 kB memory and 100 MHz clock speed. The test card and the COTS electronic components that were tested can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: The Test Card designed 12 candidate components. The component numbers given in Table 1 correspond directly to the numbers given in yellow font on the figure. The components indicated with white font are used during the testing for power management and latch-up *simulations*.

The control card was fed a voltage between 8 V and 12 V via a terminal connector and generated 5.0 V and 3.3 V both for internal use and for feeding the components on the test card. Each power, relay, analog and digital connection is carried using separate connectors between the test card and the control card. The control card includes a MAX6373 watchdog, an LMT01 temperature sensor and RS485 circuits that operate throughout the SEE radiation test. These components function to monitor the DUT's responsivity and its operational status. The control card has software in MPLAB written in C to monitor the test procedure.

Testing Measurements and Results

Overall, the objectives of the experiment could mostly be fulfilled. The description of testing measurements for each component and the results are explained below.

Testing was performed at UMCG-PARTEC with 150 and 190 MeV protons. Every component was tested for 300 seconds with a flux of 1×10^9 protons/cm²/s until a fluence of 3×10^{11} protons/cm² was reached for all components. The beamline delivered to the DUTs after the collimator had an area of 2 mm x 2 mm with uniformity of ± 10 %.

Dynamic tests were performed on all DUTs with the procedure detailed below.

- Control card was powered on.
- An initialization sequence was sent to establish communication with the control card
- The specific bypass relay for the DUT was activated.
- The current driven by the DUT was checked.
- The control and test cards were powered off.

Testing Measurements and Results

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A. TPS2420RSAT

A functionality SEE test was performed on this power manager. A latch-up configuration was simulated using resistor blocks. In the regular configuration the resistor block was made to draw 60 mA current, and in the latch-up configuration the resistor block was made to draw 600 mA current. The two scenarios were simulated successively during the SEE testing. The current drawn from a functional power manager was expected to switch off the resistor block when the latch-up current was simulated and to switch on when the latch-up configuration was over. No functional error was observed during the 150 MeV and 190 MeV proton tests which is consistent with the literature where the SEE of the device was investigated for protons with kinetic energies equal to and more than 50 MeV [1].

B. MAX891LEUA+T

The procedure explained in section A for TPS2420RSAT was repeated for this power manager as well. Functional errors were not observed during the tests. The results from the 150 MeV and 190 MeV proton tests agree with literature [1].

C. MAX3485AEASA+

This interface transceiver was successively sent control bits “01010101” and the response bits were checked for any discrepancies throughout the tests. During the test with 150 MeV protons the observed MBU number was 150 and the SEU number was 5. The total cross section was calculated to be $5.17 \pm 0.42 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for 150 MeV protons. 145 MBUs and 12 SEUs were observed during the test with 190 MeV protons and the total SEE cross section was calculated as $5.23 \pm 0.42 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The cross sections and their errors with respect to proton energies (15, 30, 60, 150 and 190 MeV) are shown in blue dots and the 2-parameter Bendel Fit with Bendel parameters [2] are shown with blue dashed line in Fig. 2.

D. AM26LS31AIDG4 and AM26LS31AIDG4

The procedure detailed in section C was repeated for this interface receiver and interface driver duo. 18 MBUs and 5 SEUs were observed during the test with 150 MeV protons and the total SEE cross section was calculated to be $7.67 \pm 1.60 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for 150 MeV protons. 15 MBUs and 4 SEUs were observed during the test with 190 MeV protons and the total SEE cross section was calculated to be $6.33 \pm 1.44 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. In Fig. 2, the cross sections and their errors found for all three proton energies (15, 30, 60, 150 and 190 MeV) and their errors with respect to proton energies are shown in orange triangles and the 2-parameter Bendel Fit with Bendel parameters [2] are shown with orange dashed line. As shown in Fig. 2, the cross sections measured at 150 MeV and 190 MeV deviate significantly from the expected trend based on the two-parameter Bendel fit to the lower-energy data. The measured cross sections at these higher energies are lower than those observed at 30 MeV and 60 MeV, which is counterintuitive given the energy dependence of SEU cross sections. This discrepancy likely indicates an issue with data acquisition rather than reflecting the true number of upsets. Notably, the 150 MeV and 190 MeV tests were conducted at a high flux of $10^9 \text{ p/cm}^2/\text{s}$. Due to the shorter exposure time needed to reach the target fluence of $3 \times 10^{11} \text{ p/cm}^2$, the number of recorded SEU events may have been limited by readout speed or data logging constraints, resulting in an underestimation of the actual upset number.

Figure 2: The cross sections with respect to proton energies of MAX3485AEASA+ are shown with blue dots and their 2-parameter Bendel fit is shown with blue dashed line. The cross sections with respect to proton energies of AM26LS31AIDG4/AM26LS31AIDG4 are shown with orange triangles and their 2-parameter Bendel fit are shown with the orange dashed line. The 2-parameter Bendel function parameters are shown on the legend.

E. MX30LF2G28AD-TI

This NAND 2 Gbit Flash Memory with 4 kB page size and 8-bit error correction code was checked for any discrepancies in its response bits to the control bits "01010101" that were sent to it successively during the test. Unlike prior studies done on similar flash memory parts with 2 kB page size and 4-bit error correction code where SEUs and MBUs were observed [3], no errors were observed during the tests for this specific device. An upper limit of $3.33 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ was found. However, during the 150 MeV test campaign, both before and during testing, the control bits remained stable at '10000001'. Notably, the '10000000' pattern occasionally transitioned to '00000000'. This behavior is not believed to be caused by SEEs but is instead attributed to faulty register unrelated to the test.

G. LMT01DQXR

The number of high and low square waves read by this temperature sensor was compared with each other. A difference between the number of high and low square waves different than 0 was accepted to be an indication of an SEE. During the test with 150 MeV and 190 MeV protons, no error was observed and an upper limit of $3.33 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ was found.

H. SE555DR

In this programmable timer the number of high and low square waves, corresponding to the timer's frequencies, were read and counted by a microcontroller. There was an increase in the difference between the high and low wave numbers during the tests with 150 and 190 MeV proton test sessions where both wave numbers decreased in time. However, the rate at which the low wave number decreased was slower than that of the high wave number. It was observed that although a 2.0 cm × 2.0 cm collimator was used the ceramic timing capacitor used the DUTs were placed approximately 15 cm downstream, allowing beam straggling to irradiate areas beyond the intended target. Based on literature regarding radiation effects on ceramic capacitors [4] it is suggested that exposure of the ceramic timing capacitor may explain the differences observed in high and low wave number behavior across these three test campaigns.

However, even in pre-test data from the programmable timer at 15 MeV proton energy, it was observed that the difference between the low and high square wave counts varied over time. In conclusion, the KBRTK test results for the SE555DR programmable timer are inconclusive; further studies using a different testing method are required.

I. ADC128S102CIMT

For this 12-bit ADC the expected value of 2.5 ± 0.05 V was compared to the corresponding digital output value 2048. A threshold of 0.05 V was set based on the variations in the expected value found in measurements taken before the test. During the test recorded values above 2.55 V or below 2.45 V were counted as SEU or MBU. No SEUs or MBUs were observed throughout the tests done with neither 150 MeV nor 190 MeV protons.

J. MAX5253BEAP+

This 12-bit DAC was sent bits corresponding to a specific reference voltage and values above and below this threshold was counted as SEU and MBU. During the test with 150 MeV protons, the reference voltages were 31 ± 8 mV. As can be seen in Fig. 3, the voltage readout during the test started to decrease then increase with respect to time, exceeding the 39-mV upper threshold. The drawn current was stable throughout the test.

Figure 3: The voltage readout of the DAC, MAX5253BEAP+, during the 150 MeV proton test with respect to time.

For the test with 190 MeV protons, the reference voltages were measured as 383 ± 4 mV. During the test, until approximately the 200th second into the irradiation, the readout voltages were stable between these values with some outliers that could be counted as SEUs. After 200 s, the voltage readout had an abrupt offset of 12 mV. The current drawn was stable throughout the test. The DAC test results from tests with protons at 5 energies (15, 30, 60, 150 and 190 MeV) show that DAC is sensitive to proton radiation and not fit to be used during space missions.

Figure 4: The voltage readout of the DAC, MAX5253BEAP+, during the 190 MeV proton test with respect to time.

K. BC857BS,115

The current drawn by this transistor was monitored throughout the tests with 15 MeV, 30 MeV, 60 MeV, 150 MeV and 190 MeV protons to observe total ionizing dose (TID) effects. The current drawn by the device was observed to be stable during all five test sessions.

These results are presented in the Master’s Thesis of Mehlika Zeynep Arslan, supervised by Prof. Dr. M. Bilge Demirköz, titled “Development of a Proton and Electron Sensitive Radiation Monitor for Space and Stratospheric Test Flights” defended on the 11th of August, 2025.

References:

[1] J. Budroweit, N. Aksteiner, T. Firchau, J. Haseker, “Compendium of current proton-induced radiation effects results on integrated power supervisors,” in RADECS., Virtual Conference, 2020, pp. 1-3.

[2] Proton Test Guideline Development – Lessons Learned, NASA, Washington, D.C., USA, 2022, pp 28-33.

[3] “Single-Event Effects Proton Test Report MX30LF4G18AC,” Hirex, Toulouse, France, Rep. HRX/SEE/00656, 2017.

[4] DJ Hamman and CL Hanks. Radiation effects design handbook. section 3-electrical insulating materials and capacitors. Technical report, NASA, 1971.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an ‘X’ next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	x
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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